

THE ROLE OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN DRIVING ORGANIZATIONAL SUCCESS: EVIDENCE FROM PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The study aims to investigate the impact of human resource management (HRM) practice in contributing to the success of the organization in the Pakistani environment. It particularly addresses recruitment and selection, training and development, performance management, compensation and rewards and employee engagement and retention, their role on organizational performance, competitiveness and long-term sustainability. The research design adopted was a quantitative design that utilized a structured questionnaire to a sample of 350 respondents who consisted of public sector organizations, private firms, non-governmental organization, and multinational corporations. The data were discussed using the descriptive statistics, and the results were depicted in graphs and tables to demonstrate demographic traits and attitudes towards HRM practices. The findings indicate that the HRM practices are greatly seen to be transparent, equitable, and aligned to organizational objectives. According to the respondents, merit-based recruitment, training in line with organizational goal, supportive feedback process, attractive remuneration package, and HR policies that emphasize retention have been rated as positive. Although these are positive trends, performance management consistency and reward fairness are identified as areas that need to be improved. In general, the research results reveal that successful HRM activities have a close association with organizational success in regards to goal attainment, improved performance and development in the long-run. The research has added to the existing sparse body of empirical literature on the topic of HRM and organizational success in Pakistan by offering empirical evidence-based findings on the role played by HR practices as strategic driving forces as opposed to administrative functions. The implications of the findings are good in both the practical aspect of the managers as well as the policy makers in the quest to empower their HR systems, and also enhance the study of HRM in the emerging economies.

INTRODUCTION

The modern era has seen the human resource management being considered as a foundation of organizational growth and sustainability. The highly competitive and globalized markets do not only evaluate organizations based on their financial resources or level of technology but also their capacity to manage and utilize well their human resource (Lee et al., 2019). The human resource role has changed over decades as its role has evolved to become more of an administrative role but has now become a strategic partner with direct contribution to the organizational performance (Irfan et al., 2023). This change has put HRM in the centre of organizational strategies to ensure increased productivity, innovation and sustainability in the long run (Ahmad et al., 2020).

The present day organizations have been faced with unparalleled challenges including technological upheaval and market turbulence as well as fluctuating employee demands and globalization (Munir et al., 2019). Such issues require adaptive ways of addressing them to enable the organizations not just to survive but to perform well. To achieve these challenges, human resources, which are also known as the most valuable asset of any organization, are very crucial (Ahmad & Museera, 2024). Appropriate HRM practices can guarantee that employees are properly recruited, trained, motivated and maintained thus contributing their efforts towards the greater organizational goals (Alim et al., 2025). In this regard, HRM turns out to be an interface that links employee performance with organizational success.

The HRM importance is especially observed in recruitment and selection domains. Clear, meritocratic recruitment procedures aid organizations to recruit and retain talent which is in line with organizational culture and objectives (Jawaad et al., 2019). Equally, the fair selection processes will promote employee confidence within the organization and foster the aspect of high-performance culture. Whenever employees feel that they are treated fairly during recruitment and selection, then they will be motivated, loyal and committed to the goals of the organisation (Malik et al., 2020). Recruitment is not that simply a process of filling vacancies, however; it is a strategic process,

which determines future workforce and has a direct impact on organizational competitiveness (Bhatti et al., 2022).

Another important aspect of training and development is a part of HRM practices that lead to the success of the organization. The capacity of employees to constantly update their skills and competencies is critical in the modern economy which is more knowledge based. Companies that invest in strategic-oriented training programs are more likely to manage the dynamics in the market, innovate and attain sustainable growth (Afshar & Shah, 2025). Training in addition to developing skill will promote employee engagement and morale, which will give employees an indication that their personal and professional development is being appreciated. This, in its turn, enhances the organizational loyalty and decreases the turnover rates, which is one of the most important factors of long-term success (Imtiaz et al., 2025).

The performance management systems are also central to the performance of organization. Adequate and transparent performance appraisals will give employees constructive feedback, reward performance, and give areas of improvement (Imtiaz et al., 2025). The systems promote performance culture and accountability. Performance management, when performed well, assists in aligning personal objectives with the organizational objectives, all members of workforce would help in achieving a common vision of success (Naseer et al., 2023). On the other hand, biased or unequal appraisal systems may destroy trust and negatively affect the motivation of employees, which is why it is significant to have a strong and just approach to the performance management (Afshar & Shah, 2025).

Another aspect of the HRM practices that directly affect the organizational performance is compensation and reward systems. The application of competitive salaries, benefits as well as rewarding employees with rewards that are linked to their performance is crucial towards ensuring that employees are motivated to reach greater levels of productivity and innovativeness (Aftab et al., 2023). Furthermore, employee satisfaction, turnover, and positive working environment can be improved

through reward systems that are considered just and open-minded. Compensation does not just entail the money factor of remuneration but also recognition and career growth opportunities and general experience of working and all this leads to a successful organization (Atif, 2024).

The strategic function of HRM is also strengthened by employee engagement and employee retention policies. Involved employees are more devoted, efficient and creative, whereas retention strategies enable organizations to save on their expenditure on human resource (Shah & Soomro, 2023). In competitive employment market, organizations that lose their most skilled employees are at a great risk, which include loss of knowledge, costs of recruiting employees and loss of productivity (Lee et al., 2019). Successful HRM policies which facilitate job satisfaction, career development as well as the well being of the employees are thus critical towards maintaining competitive advantage (Awan et al., 2023).

The relationship between HRM practices and the success of the organization is particularly high in the new economies like Pakistan. As Pakistan is becoming increasingly a part of the global economy, organizations in the country are under increasing pressure to become more efficient, competitive, and adaptable (Jamal et al., 2021). Traditionally, HRM has been perceived in most organizations in Pakistan as an administrative role and not as a source of success. This perception is however shifting fast as companies are interested in realizing that good HRM can boost employee performance, innovate and help organizational resilience in volatile settings (Fang et al., 2022). Specifically, other sectors like banking, manufacturing, education, and services are turning to the trend of modern HRM practices as a way of keeping pace with other competitors in the domestic and international markets (Saeed et al., 2019).

Political instability, fluctuations in the economy, and regulations are considered to be external factors that could affect organizational success in Pakistan. In spite of these, HRM is offering a channel through which corporations can develop internal capabilities that allow it to absorb the external pressures (Raza & Khan, 2022). As an example, organizations can be resilient and adaptable by building talent

acquisition, skills growth, and employee engagement. Furthermore, the focus on equity, openness, and employee empowerment in the practices of HR is especially applicable in environments where the diversity of the workforce, the generational disparities and social demands changes fast (Shah & Soomro, 2023).

Another role of HRM in Pakistan is related to dealing with cultural and social dynamics which define the workplace practices. The workers of the country are not homogeneous since they have different educational background, skills, and socio-cultural values (Zeeshan & Qazi, 2023). Good HRM will see to it that this diversity will be managed in a constructive way that will encourage inclusion and equity in organizations (Ali & Brandl, 2017). Moreover, because the young generations are entering into the workforce with more expectations when it comes to professional growth and work-life balance, HRM has a responsibility to adjust to this expectation without ruining the performance of the organization. Therefore, the HRM practices implementation in Pakistan is not just the prerequisite of the successful functioning of the organization but also the factor of the social and economic advance (Rana & Malik, 2017).

The research is aimed at exploring the level of organizational success that HRM practices bring in Pakistan. The research aims at empirically demonstrating the strategic significance of HRM by emphasizing on major dimensions, including recruitment and selection, training and development, performance management, compensation and rewards, and employee engagement and retention (Pandita & Ray, 2018). The results are likely to enlighten us on the superiority or inferiority of the existing HRM practices in Pakistan, as well as provide information on how organizations can streamline their human capital strategies to achieve more success (Hassan, 2022).

This significance of the research is that it can have an impact on theory and practice. In theoretical terms, it adds to the ever-increasing amount of knowledge that makes HRM a driver of organization performance instead of a support one (Memon et al., 2021). Practically speaking, it provides practical learning to managers, policymakers and

organizational leaders in Pakistan who are endeavoring to make a sustainable growth in growing competitive markets. This research contributes to the body of knowledge by emphasizing the importance of HRM in determining the organizational performance and the need of organizations to invest in their human resource and prioritize on human capital as the source of long term benefit (Fahim, 2018).

To sum up, the ever-changing environment in which contemporary organizations are established, requires that human resource management be considered as the key component of the strategy and not as a secondary process. The role of HRM in the organizational success has never been as important in Pakistan where organizations are surviving through a complicated economic, social, and cultural landscape. The evidence collected during this study aims to show that in case of strategic implementation of HRM, the employee performance is enhanced, as well as the organizational performance, competitiveness, and sustainability. This preconditions an intensive analysis of the HRM practices in Pakistan and the possibility to turn organizations into strong and efficient organizations in a dynamic world.

Literature Review

Evolution of Human Resource Management

The current decades have seen a significant change in human resource management where the management has ceased to be merely an administrative role but an organizational partner in success (Nawaz & Naseem, 2023). In early days, HRM used to be concerned with record-keeping, payroll, and compliance where it had minimal impact on the wider organizational strategies. With time though, organizations have understood that employees are a rare resource that leads to productivity, innovation and long-term growth. This awareness made HRM an important aspect of strategy management (Saqib et al., 2022). Modern HRM role goes beyond the duty of providing care to the employees and seeking to match the contribution of the workforce to the organizational goals. Subsequently, HRM is now considered as an indispensable force to long term success.

Recruitment and Selection as Strategic Functions

HRM practices are based on the recruitment and selection. Good recruitment will help organizations to get access to the right talent, whereas equitable and transparent selection processes will help in ensuring that the best candidates are recruited (Reis et al., 2019). Recruiting is no longer done to fill vacant positions, but it has become a strategic process that helps determine the future trend of the workforce. When organizations embrace merit and open recruitment systems, they are in a position to give employees a sense of trust and commitment which gives them an edge in competition (Abraham et al., 2015). Conversely, discriminatory or cloudy processes of selection will threaten the morale of employees and performance within organizations (Sparrow et al., 2013). The role of recruitment and selection in the Pakistani setting is even more important in the context of establishing fairness and equity in organizations because the cultural and social expectations that govern the workplace dynamics have a significant impact on the recruitment and selection.

Training and Development for Capacity Building

The practice of training and development has become one of the most important HRM practices that lead directly to organizational flexibility and strength. The high rate at which technology is changing and the rate of globalization has necessitated the process of updating the skills of employees by the organization in a continuous manner (Zubair et al., 2021). Organizational-oriented training programs do not only improve the personal capacities, but they result in innovation and efficiency at the organizational level (Azhar & Choudhry, 2016). Moreover, development programs are an indicator to employees that their progress is appreciated thus enhancing the drive and commitment (Khan et al., 2017). Training and development is essential in Pakistan where the industries are struggling to keep up with global standards, to ensure that their skills remain updated to help them increase productivity as well as boost economic growth that relies on knowledge.

Performance Management and Organizational Effectiveness

The key area in the alignment of employee contributions with the organizational goals is performance management. It promotes a culture of performance and offers motivation to employees as well as accountability because fair and clear appraisal systems build trust in them. Positive feedback processes make employees know their strengths and areas of improvement to be able to continue developing (Janjua et al., 2019). When organizations have been able to connect performance management to the wider objectives, chances of efficiency, innovation, and sustainable success are high (Aslam & Sarwar, 2010). Performance management, however, may also be a dissatisfaction factor in cases where there is a perception of bias, inconsistency, and non-transparency among the employees. In some countries such as Pakistan where personal contacts and informal systems tend to determine performance management within organizations, fair performance management systems should be put in place to enhance organizational credibility and success.

Compensation, Rewards and Employee Motivation

One of the most overt practices of HRM is compensation and rewards. Salaries, benefits and recognition systems are competitive and remain in the centre stage of motivating employees and increasing their level of satisfaction (Malik et al., 2020). Properly designed reward system does not only motivate performance but also helps to retain employees which helps in saving the cost of recruitment and continuity in the organization knowledge. Financial remuneration is not the only way through which the compensation is applied; other forms of compensation are career growth opportunities, recognition and conducive work environments (Irfan et al., 2023). The Pakistani environment is no different because competitive compensation enhances the ability of an organization to retain and attract the best talent in a highly competitive job market. On the contrary, unfair or inadequate reward perception may lead to

a high rate of turnover and low engagement of employees (Ahmad et al., 2020).

Employee Engagement and Retention

Employee engagement has been generally known to be a defining factor of organizational success. The employees who are engaged have an increased commitment, productivity, and innovation. The retention strategies are also crucial because losing efficient staff does not only derail the operations of the organization but also adds the costs related to the recruitment and training (Iqbal et al., 2017). Organizations with HRM practices that facilitate job satisfaction, career growth and work life balance are likely to retain their employees. Engagement and retention strategies in ensuring stability in organizational competitiveness can be of particular importance in Pakistan, where economic uncertainty and migration trends determine the stability of the workforce (Wen et al., 2022).

HRM and Organizational Success

HRM practices have an overall effect on the success of an organization and this has been well recorded in the global literature. Recruitment and selection will be used to attract the right talent; training will facilitate the ability of the workforce; performance management will create accountability; compensation will create motivation to work; and engagement will create loyalty. The practices, when properly incorporated, tend to ensure that the efforts of the employees are in line with the organizational strategies, leading to a higher performance, a stronger competitiveness as well as, sustainability (Sarwar et al., 2016). Financial results are not the only factors indicating organizational success but also the capacity to be innovative, adaptable, and develop a motivated workforce. HRM is an effective stabilizing factor in a not so stable environment that is Pakistan considering the economic instability, political instability, and lack of skilled personnel that affect organizations in this country (Khalid et al., 2016).

The Pakistani Context of HRM

The HRM modern practices have been on the increase within the past two decades in Pakistan due to globalization, technological advancement and heightened competition. In the past, HR was

regarded in most organizations within the country as an administrative department that aimed at maintaining records and compliances (Arshad et al., 2014). Nonetheless, as the human capital concept has become more of a strategic resource, HRM currently is more integrated into the process of organizational planning and decision-making (Khan et al., 2016). Banking, manufacturing, education, and service sectors are at the forefront in implementing HRM practices that are focusing on fairness, development, and well being of employees. However, there are still weaknesses of poor resources, resistance to change and difference in organizational cultures (Sheikh et al., 2016).

Research Gap and Relevance

Although the role of HRM as a source of organizational success is becoming more and more widely acknowledged, there is a scarcity of empirical studies that examine the connection between HRM and organizational success in the Pakistani setting. Although the global literature offers a great deal of evidence about the strategic role of HRM, local aspects of culture, economy, and organizational practices require specific studies. This research will fill this gap by studying the role that the HRM practices play in determining the success of an organization in Pakistan with respect to recruitment, training, performance management, compensation and engagement. The study contributes to the current body of knowledge in addition to offering practical insights to the managers and policymakers by giving evidence presented by Pakistan.

Problem Statement

In the current competitive business world, challenges connected to the globalization, technology-induced disruption, and workforce diversity continue to mount in organizations in Pakistan. Although the concept of human resource management has been accepted throughout the world as a strategic force that can make or break organizations, most of the Pakistani organizations are yet to come to terms with incorporating the HRM within their mainstream strategies. The process of recruitment is not always transparent, training programs are not always synchronized with

the organizational performance, the performance management system is viewed as biased. Equally, rewarding and payment systems are not necessarily competitive to retain the best employees, and employee engagement is not always steady. These weaknesses indicate a significant gap in the current knowledge on the role of HRM practices in contributing to the performance and success of organizations in the long run in Pakistan, and thus, research to establish the effectiveness of such practices in systematic manner is required.

Objectives of the Study

1. To investigate how organizations in Pakistan are successful based on recruitment and selection practices.
2. To determine the importance of training and development in employee performance and development of organizations.
3. To analyze the effectiveness of performance management, compensation and reward system in motivating employees and enhancing organizational performance.
4. To examine the relevance of employee engagement and retention strategies in the long-term organizational success of organizations in Pakistan.

Significance of the Study

The study is very important to both scholars and practitioners highlighting the strategic importance of HRM to spur organizational success. To organizations in Pakistan, the results offer practical information regarding how the processes of recruitment, training, performance management, compensation, and engagement can be streamlined to realize sustainable development. The study is also significant to policy makers who would want to enhance the development of the workforce on the national level. The study fills a gap in the current literature, which enhances the general knowledge of HRM in emergent economies besides providing practical guidelines to managers and the HR professionals. Finally, it strengthens the significance of human capital as one of the factors of organizational competitiveness and sustainability.

Methodology

The research design used in this study was quantitative research design that was to be used in analyzing the role of human resource management (HRM) practices in the organizational success in Pakistan. An organized questionnaire was constructed where the various dimensions of HRM were targeted that is recruitment and selection, training and development, performance management, compensation and rewards as well as employee engagement and retention. The scales had close-ended questions with a five-point Likert scale of Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree, and this was the standardized responses that could be analyzed statistically.

The sample size was 350 respondents who work in various organizations such as the government in various institutions and organizations, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), as well as multinational organizations. This allocation was aimed at having a broad range of views in the fields of sectors and increasing the external validity of the findings. A mixture of convenience and random sampling was used to reach the participants in the various levels of professionalism and organizations. The process of data collection has been done by both physical distribution of questionnaires and over the online platforms to have broader coverage and to receive prompt response. Respondents were asked to give demographic information such as gender, age, education, work experience, and organizational affiliation so that they may put the findings into perspective and enable them to carry out a comparative study within the subgroups.

The statistical techniques used in coding and analyzing the data were descriptive and inferential statistics. The demographic features were shown in

numbers and graphs and the answers to the statements on the HRM practice were tabulated to make them clear and precise. Frequency distributions and percentages were also determined to show the predominant trends and comparative interpretations were made to show the patterns and variations in all variables.

This research design gave us a methodological framework on which we could measure the contribution of HRM practices to organizational performance and long-term success. The combination of graphical and tabular format of presentation made results easier to read and provided more information about the perceptions of employees on the HRM practices in their respective organizations.

Data Analysis

Data analysis is the systematic procedure of inspecting, cleansing, transforming, and modeling information with an aim of finding potentially valuable information, informing a conclusion and aiding a decision-making. It is the use of statistical and logical methods to define trends, reveal patterns, and determine the relationships in raw data (Butt & Yazdani, 2023). The practice makes an assortment of numbers and facts more useful and actionable by going beyond descriptions to consider the cause and the consequences that could happen in the future. This can help organizations in all industries- business and science to include healthcare and government- to make better decisions by moving beyond their intuition-driven guesswork to evidence-based strategies, which eventually maximize performance, forecast the future and create innovation (Sadia, 2020).

Results

Figure No. 1 Gender Distribution of the Respondents

The gender distribution of the respondents as illustrated in *Figure 1* indicated that among the total sample of 350 respondents, 209 individuals were male and thus representing 59.7 of this figure and 141 were female and thus representing 40.3. This shows that the males respondents were the majority with a gap of close to 20 percent-points over

the females. Despite an equal representation between two genders, the males predominate, which implies an unequal distribution. This type of demographic data is essential because it will give a clear understanding of the sample make-up and will previously point to the possible impact of gender representation that may be made on the overall results of the study.

Figure No. 2 Age Group of the Respondents

As shown in *Figure 2*, the age of the respondents indicates that the highest percentage was 30-39 age group (38.3), which had 134 respondents. It was followed by the 20-29 years age group which had 123 respondents (35.1%) close behind. The largest number of participants was 40-49 years bracket (62

respondents or 17.7 percent), whereas the smallest number was 50 years and above with a participation of only 31 respondents (8.9 percent). These findings imply that the sample was mainly consisting of young and middle-aged people, and relatively fewer older ones. Such a distribution indicates that the

results of the study can also be very much influenced by the attitude and experiences of the respondents who are in the early to mid-career stages.

Figure No. 3 Education Level of the Respondents

The qualification of the respondents in terms of education as shown in *Figure 3* has revealed that the highest number of respondents have a Bachelor degree with 161 representing 46.0 percent of the sample. This was then succeeded by 119 respondents (34.0%) who had a Master degree. Only a smaller percentage (12.9), 45 people (45 delivered an MPhil) and only 25 individuals (7.1) had a PhD.

The distribution proves that many of the sample consist of people that have undergraduate degrees and postgraduate degrees and few of the participants have advanced research degrees. This kind of educational profile offers a good academic basis among the respondents, as well as represents the different degrees of expertise and specialization of the group.

Figure No. 4 Work Experience of the Respondents

Figure 4 of the work experience distribution provided by the respondents reveals that the greatest number of respondents had experience of between 2-5 years with 120 respondents (34.3%). It was then succeeded by 105 respondents (30.0%) who have 6-10 years of professional experience. A significant percentage (21.4) of 75 participants had greater than

10 years of experience and the least number of 50 participants had less than 2 years experience. This distribution emphasizes that the sample mainly includes early to mid-career professionals, and there is a large share of experienced people, which is making the perspective rather balanced with the different stages of careers.

Figure No. 5 Organization Type of the Respondents

As Figure 5 shows, the organizational affiliation of the respondents means that almost 50 percent of the participants (174, 49.7 percent) were in the private sector, which is the most represented group. This was succeeded by 92 (26.3) respondents in the public sector and 50 (14.3) respondents in the non-governmental organizations (NGO). The least

number of 34 people (9.7%) were employed in multinational corporations. The distribution indicates that the involvement of the organizations of the private sector is high, and the significant input is also represented by the organizations of the public, NGOs, and multinational corporations, thus providing a diversity of organizations in the study sample.

Table 1: Recruitment and Selection (n = 350)

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
My organization uses transparent and merit-based recruitment practices	10 (2.9%)	25 (7.1%)	49 (14.0%)	156 (44.6%)	110 (31.4%)
HR ensures fair opportunities for all candidates during selection	7 (2.0%)	21 (6.0%)	44 (12.6%)	160 (45.7%)	118 (33.7%)

The data provided in Table 1 on the recruitment and selection practices demonstrate that the respondents have a rather positive perception on the practices in general. Most of the respondents concurred (44.6) and strongly concurred (31.4), that their organizations were characterized by

transparency and merit-based recruiting procedures, and a very minor percentage did not agree (7.1) or strongly did not agree (2.9). In the same question, inquiring whether the HR can provide equal chances to the applicants in terms of selection most of the respondents said yes (45.7%), strongly yes

(33.7%), less yes (12.6%), and no (8.0% combined). According to these findings, the perceptions regarding the recruitment and selection practices in the surveyed organizations can be described as

predominantly fair and transparent, which helps to increase the credibility of the HR processes and create the trust among employees in the organizational practices of hiring.

Table 2: Training and Development (n = 350)

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Employees are regularly provided with training opportunities	15 (4.3%)	30 (8.6%)	60 (17.1%)	150 (42.9%)	95 (27.1%)
Training programs are aligned with organizational goals	12 (3.4%)	26 (7.4%)	55 (15.7%)	162 (46.3%)	95 (27.1%)

The results in Table 2 on training and development practices reflect very much positive perception of the respondents. Most of them were in agreement (42.9% or strongly in agreement (27.1%)) that they are offered regular training opportunities, with very few disagreeing (8.6% or strongly disagreeing (4.3%)). Likewise, the vast majority of the respondents said that training programs are consistent with organizational objectives (46.3%),

and that more people said that they were consistent (27.1%), and others were neutral (15.7%). These findings indicate that the organizations that were surveyed are highly investing in their workforce development and are making sure that the training programs contribute to the overall organizational goals, further contributing to workforce and companies performance.

Table 3: Performance Management (n = 350)

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Performance appraisals are fair and unbiased	18 (5.1%)	32 (9.1%)	72 (20.6%)	145 (41.4%)	83 (23.7%)
Employees receive constructive feedback	14 (4.0%)	28 (8.0%)	60 (17.1%)	162 (46.3%)	86 (24.6%)

Table 3 shows the outcomes of the performance management and it indicates that the respondents tend to have positive perceptions about the appraisal and feedback practices. Most of them (41.4) or strongly agreed (23.7) that performance appraisal is fair and unbiased and a significant percentage (20.6) were neither in agreement nor disagreed, and a smaller percentage (14.2) was in strong disagreement. Similarly, in response to the

question of getting constructive feedback, the majority (46.3% and 24.6% respectively) reported agreeing (or strongly agreeing) with few (12.0% summed up) disagreeing. Such results show that, although performance management systems are mostly viewed as fair and supportive, the occurrence of the neutral responses means that there might be inconsistency or lack of clarity in the appraisal and feedback practices amongst some of the employees.

Table 4: Compensation and Rewards (n = 350)

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Compensation and benefits are competitive	20 (5.7%)	38 (10.9%)	70 (20.0%)	142 (40.6%)	80 (22.9%)
Reward systems motivate employees	14 (4.0%)	30 (8.6%)	62 (17.7%)	158 (45.1%)	86 (24.6%)

Table 4 on compensations and rewards shows that the overall responses of respondents are positive. Most of them (40.6 -22.9) agreed or strongly agreed that their organization provides competitive compensation and benefits, but 20.0% of them were neutral and a smaller percentage (16.6% amalgamated) disagreed. In the same way, majority of the respondents (45.1) or strongly disagreed (24.6) that reward systems can be effective

motivators, 17.7% were neutral, and only 12.6% disagreed. These results indicate that compensation and reward practices are widely regarded as equitable and encouraging, yet the neutral answers point out to the fact that some of the employees might feel that this area of their work requires to be improved to make compensation and rewards correspond to the performance standards.

Table 5: Employee Engagement and Retention (n = 350)

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
HR policies enhance job satisfaction	9 (2.6%)	20 (5.7%)	54 (15.4%)	165 (47.1%)	102 (29.1%)
Effective strategies to retain talent	15 (4.3%)	35 (10.0%)	60 (17.1%)	150 (42.9%)	90 (25.7%)

The findings in Table 5 on employee engagement and retention show that the respondents have a largely positive outlook. Most people (47.129.1) strongly agreed or agreed that HR policies increase the job satisfaction with a low percentage (8.3) disagreements and 15.4 non-neutral views. On the same question, most respondents stated that their effective strategies to retain talent were agreeable (42.9%), strongly agreeable (25.7%), and 17.1%

were neutral and 14.3% disagreeable. These results can be interpreted as indicating that the HR practices within the surveyed organizations can be considered as mostly effective in facilitating job satisfaction and job retention yet the existence of neutral and disagreeing reports suggests that some areas could use a reinforcement to guarantee the stable employee engagement and retention.

Table 6: Organizational Success (n = 350)

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
HR practices contribute to achieving goals	6 (1.7%)	18 (5.1%)	45 (12.9%)	165 (47.1%)	116 (33.1%)
Effective HR enhances organizational performance	5 (1.4%)	15 (4.3%)	42 (12.0%)	168 (48.0%)	120 (34.3%)
HR policies link to long-term success	8 (2.3%)	20 (5.7%)	48 (13.7%)	160 (45.7%)	114 (32.6%)

Table 6 on the organizational success findings shows that there is a high degree of consistency among the respondents when it comes to the role of HR practices in the performance and long-term growth. Most (47.1) of the respondents and a good percentage (33.1) of participants agreed or strongly agreed that HR practices help in meeting organizational goals with only 6.8% responding to the contrary. In the same vein, the majority (48.0) or strongly agreed (34.3) that effective HR improves

the performance of an organization with only a minor fraction (5.7 in total) of the participants disagreeing. In addition, there was agreement with 45.7% strongly agreeing and 32.6 agreeing that HR policies are related to long-term success and only 8.0% disagreed. These findings create a distinct agreement that good HR practices are central to the success of an organization, which supports their strategic significance in the alignment of the human capital to the long-term goals.

Discussion

The results of the study are a good indication that human resource management (HRM) practices are important drivers of organizational success in the Pakistani environment. The demographic profile represents good balance among the respondents in terms of age, education and category of organization, majority of them being in the private sector. This variety increases the confidence of the outcomes, stating that the insights are not industry or sector-specific.

The discussion has established that recruitment and selection processes in most organizations are viewed to be transparent and based on merit with a significant majority of the respondents stating that equal opportunities are offered during the hiring process. This is an indication of an increasing realization by some organizations in Pakistan to match recruitment practices with international norms of fairness and inclusivity. Nevertheless, a rather low yet significant percentage of the respondents noted that the practice of recruitment can still be enhanced in terms of transparency and objectivity in some organizations.

The area of training and development was one of the crucial areas that organizations have been doing well in but there are still gaps. Although the majority of the respondents indicated that training programs are in line with organisational objectives, almost a quarter of workers disagreed or were neutral. It means that although the structured training opportunities are becoming more important, the issues of consistency in applying them and their applicability to the job-specific needs should be discussed further to make the most of them (Irfan et al., 2023).

There was also mixed perception in performance management practices. Even though a significantly enormous proportion considered appraisals as fair and feedback as constructive, close to 30 percent of the respondents were skeptical or displeased. This is where the issue of having impartial evaluation systems comes in within the context of organizational cultures that either encourage favoritism or lack adequate feedback to raise the level of employee trust. Enhancement of appraisal systems and their greater association with performance achievement might enhance

motivation of the employees as well as their alignment with the organization (Khalid et al., 2016).

These systems of compensation and rewards were in general seen to be positive, however, one-third of the respondents had reservations. This implies that though competitive compensation systems are practiced in most organizations, discrepancies might exist in the fairness and consistency of rewarding systems (Khan et al., 2016). The reward systems are not only effective in motivating performance but also in employee retention which the results of the employee engagement and retention strengthened.

More importantly, the findings clearly prove that HRM practices have a strong relationship with the success of the organization (Munir et al., 2019). The respondents unanimously agreed that having effective HR policies help in the attainment of organizational objectives and improvement in performance and long-term sustainability. This highlights the strategic position of HRM as more than an administrative activity- it is a productivity, innovation as well as growth driver (Malik et al., 2020).

In general, it is stated in the discussion that even though the Pakistani organization is making great steps towards modern HRM practices, there are still spheres that need to be improved, especially in performance management and fairness of rewards. By tackling such challenges, the role of HRM in the process of creating sustainable organizational success will be even more developed.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The results of this research affirm the fact that human resource management is very critical in determining organizational success in Pakistan. Through the analysis on recruitment and selection, training and development, performance management, compensation and rewards, and employee engagement and retention, the research reveals that effective HRM practices can help not only to enhance employee performance, but also organizational competitiveness and sustainability. The results of the analysis of the responses provided by 350 participants demonstrated that most of the organizations are on the way to cultivating the transparent practices of recruitment, the organized

training programs, and the equitable system of compensation. Nevertheless, there are still issues to deal with in order to guarantee the uniformity of the performance management processes, reinforce the reward mechanisms, and improve employee engagement tactics. These findings underscore the fact that unlike in most Pakistani organizations where HRM has not reached its full potential, HRM is becoming an important strategic function in organizations.

Among the main findings of this study, there is the fact that open recruitment and reasonable selection methods are crucial in earning trust and engaging the appropriate talent. Companies that focus on hiring employees on the basis of merit are better placed at promoting the culture of fairness and inclusiveness, which translates into a long-term employee commitment. In the same way, organizational goal-oriented training and development initiatives equip employees with skills that would enable them to meet the fast changing technologies and market dynamics. This does not only help people but it also helps in sustaining the organizations in competitive environments.

It was discovered that performance management is one of the areas that organizations still struggle with a lot. Even though most of the respondents confirmed the presence of appraisal systems, there is concern of unfairness and inconsistency which indicates that there is a need to improve on the systems. Appraisal systems need to be converted into developmental tools by providing constructive feedback, clear performance standards and accountability systems which will ensure that appraisal systems will no longer be sources of dissatisfaction. Compensation and rewards, although perceived positively, must as well be more competitive and individual as well as team based, to give credit on individual and team contribution. The reward systems must focus on more than just the financial rewards but also the rewards in terms of recognition, career development and conducive working environment.

Employee engagement and retention concepts proved to be additional factors to ensure organizational success. Employees who are engaged are more innovative, productive and become loyal, retention saves the expenses of turnover and

recruitment. To retain their finest employees, organizations in Pakistan need to make investments to the policies that promote job satisfaction, work-life balance, and career advancement. This is more so when migration and economic uncertainties usually cause instability in the workforce.

There are a number of recommendations that can be drawn based on these findings. The recruitment processes in organizations should be institutionalized by transparent and merit-based recruitment processes where every candidate has equal opportunities to the rest. The training and development programs should constantly be revised depending on the changing organizational and industrial requirements. The performance management systems must be redesigned to be more focused on fairness, positive feedback, and strategic alignment. The compensation and rewards should be designed in such a way that should be competitive taking into account various inputs towards organizational success. Lastly, the focus of the employee engagement efforts must be healthy, reward, and career development to retain employees and create a long-term investment. Through these recommendations, the organizations in Pakistan will be able to optimize the efforts of their human resources and have sustainable success in the ever-competitive markets.

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